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Assessment Of Teachers' Competence In Construction And Validation Procedure Of Mathematics Test Among Senior Secondary School Teachers In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed teachers' competence in test construction and validation procedure of Mathematics test among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study were to assess the teachers' competence in test construction based on professional training, and assess the teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test based on years of working experience, among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised to guide the study and three hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ levels of significance. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study comprises of 1,787 senior secondary schools' Mathematics teachers. The populations were obtained from one hundred and forty-five (145) senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. A sample size of 132 Mathematics teachers was selected using cluster and simple random sampling technique. Data was collected using a questionnaire titled "Test Construction and Standardization of Mathematics Test Questionnaire" (TCSMTQ) adapted from Abdullahi (2019). The instrument was validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The reliability of the items was determined using Cronbach's alpha reliability which yielded a coefficient of 0.75. Data collected were described and analyzed using statistical mean and standard deviation, percentage, independent sample t-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA). All hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$ levels of significance. The results of the study showed that, significant difference exists in teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training ($p = 0.006 < 0.05$), no significant difference in teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test based on years of working experience ($p = 0.591 > 0.05$), and significant difference exists in teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test based on educational qualification ($p = 0.001 < 0.05$) among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training among senior secondary schools' teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria differ significantly. It was therefore recommended among others that the State' Ministry of Education should organize conferences, seminars, workshops, and given pre and in-service professional training programmes on test construction to non-professional teacher.

Keywords: test construction, teachers' competence, Mathematics

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge of test construction is an essential tool needed by every teacher if learning and instructional objectives are to be effectively attained. The quality of a teacher-made test is closely linked with its ability to provide the kind of information needed regarding students' performances. It is expected that the schools should have enough valid and reliable tests for assessing their students when they have covered the curriculum content areas as well as to prepare them for external examinations. A good teacher' knowledge in Mathematics at secondary school will help students in tertiary institutions to study Mathematics and other related courses. Most students choose Mathematics in the secondary school because of their interest, ability and its relevance to their future careers. The constructed valid and reliable test done by Mathematics teachers contributed alot to the achievement of students in senior secondary schools.

A well-written test allows the teachers to accurately and consistently measure students' mastery of specific contents taught in class (Abdullahi, 2019). Likewise, poorly construction of test items can lead to inaccurate measurements of learning and provide false information regarding student performance as well as instructional effectiveness (Ngozi, Chika & Aloysius, 2013). This inaccurate measurements or errors could emanate in three categories: the first 'errors inherent in the instrument, 'errors in the use of the instrument and 'errors emanating from the responses of test takers' (Anikweze, 2016). Therefore, test construction ability and quality are fundamental tools required by any educator if teaching and learning goals are to be achieved (Abdullahi, 2019).

The systematic planning of the test requires identifying the instructional and behavioural objectives to be measured; identifying the content areas for the test, deciding on the test format and table of specifications (Osadebe, 2014). The test format is multiple choice objective test items. The table of specifications helped to establish high content validity (Ukwuije & Opara, 2012). The table of specifications could be drawn vertically and horizontally to determine the content areas and behavioural objectives for item writings. The instructional objectives as in this study were derived from the content areas of ordinary level (O/L) Mathematics curriculum. The behavioural objectives or cognitive levels include knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. It becomes pertinent to guide teachers on test construction procedures.

The procedures used in constructing the test include: planning composition of items, test theory, reliability, printing and manual preparation. The teachers and other users are expected to administer the test and score, to be guided by the manual as supported by Ukwuije and Opara (2012). Test may be composed in ascending order (preparing items or questions according to how the topics were taught), descending (setting questions starting from the last topic), and randomization (randomly selecting questions from the pool of items) (Osadebe, 2014). Test construction ability and quality are fundamental tools required by any educator if teaching and learning goals are to be achieved (Abdullahi, 2019).

For achievement test, the most important validities to establish are face and content validities. Face validity is concerned with level of English used, if the items are ambiguous, if it is multiple choice, check if they are properly keyed, if the keys come in a pattern, and if there are overlapping items (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). It is also very important to establish content validity of an achievement test as it is crucial that the test covers the content area the learners have been exposed to; reliability and usability of the tests are also established as achievement is a latent trait (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). All these are incorporated in test construction and validation procedures which each teacher should be aware of and follow to be able to set good tests, especially Mathematics teachers of senior secondary schools. **Test**

Construction

Test construction is the set of activities involved in developing and evaluating a test of some psychological function. Process of construction and standardization is an essential one. Because the test measures the educational development of all students (Prabakaran & Saravanakumar, 2020). The importance of tests in the educational system is enormous, as it provides a platform by which any significant educational objectives can be achieved (Hamafyelto, Hamman-Tukur & Hamafyelto, 2015). Every classroom teacher is expected to exhibit expertise and apply requisite test construction skills in the construction of good test items for class assessments. Teachers who served as facilitators of knowledge

must have the ability in measuring learning achievements with accuracy (Abdullahi, 2019). The competency in test construction is an essential tool needed by every teacher if learning and instructional objectives are to be effectively attained (Quansah & Amoako, 2018).

Test construction competencies include the construction of quality tests based on the principles of test construction. Inko-Tariah and Okon (2019) gave some steps in test construction as test planning, Item writing, trial testing, thereafter item analysis and Items selection. Osadebe (2014) construct test with procedures such as planning, item writing, item analysis, composition of items, test theory, reliability, printing and manual preparation. These procedures used to identify the content area, format and table specification on the test. From the perspective of Quansah and Amoako (2018), the construction of test items should follow four broad categorizations thus planning, item construction, review, and assembling.

Teachers need not be experts in educational measurement and evaluation to construct valid and reliable tests, but there are basic test construction skills which every teacher ought to possess to construct quality tests (Agu et al, 2013). Test construction skills are those abilities required for developing valid and reliable tests. It also helps a teacher obtain reliable information on students' achievement. To ascertain or measure the test construction skills of teachers requires the use of an appropriate measuring instrument. Such appropriate measuring instrument is not readily available for use in Nigerian schools mainly because much effort has not been made with respect to research reports on test construction skills of teachers (Ughamadu, Ifeyinwa, & Okaforcha, 2014).

Ogbeide and Idusogie (nd) stated that the quality of a test in terms of validity and reliability is affected by a number of factors. Some of these factors may be as a result of teacher's characteristics in terms of knowledge of test construction, experience, level of education, professionalism and gender. Since the quality of a test given by a teacher is closely linked with its ability to provide the kind of information needed regarding students' performances, a well written test allows the teacher to accurately and consistently measure students' mastery of specific contents taught in class (Camble & Hamman-Tukur, 2017). In addition, Kinyua and Okunya (2014) and Agu et al (2013), found that teacher characteristics have significant effect on the quality of test.

Olufunke (2019) possess that the test constructor (the tester) should be familiar with the parameters which a good test should possess; the tester can then begin to construct the test, which may either be a unit test or a full-fledged question paper covering all the aspects of the subject syllabus. In the same line, the guidelines for writing test items are to: choose the type of test item that measures the intended learning competence specifically, writing the test items clearly and definitively, writing the test items that will elicit performance in the learning task, writing the test items that are free from nonfunctional material, writing the test item so that irrelevant clues do not enable the uninformed student to respond correctly, writing the test item so that irrelevant factors do not prevent an informed student from responding correctly, writing the test item so that the difficulty level matches the intent of the learning competence, the age of the students to be tested, the usefulness of the results and writing more test items than the slated number of the test plan.

Basic steps in Test construction

The test planning and construction steps include: constructing the test design, weighing the test objectives, preparing questions based on blue print, assembling the questions, preparing the scoring key and the marking scheme and preparing question-wise analysis. Based on Mardapi (2012) there are nine steps that must be reached in constructing test namely: (1) Arranging the specification of test, (2) writing test, (3) understanding test, (4) Test experiment, (5) Analyzing test, (6) test revise, (7) assemble the test, (8) do the test, (9) interpreting the test results. Setting the test specification is to describe the overall characteristics that a test should have. Procedures for the preparation of test specifications include: determination of test objectives, arranging the test grille, determining the form of the test, and determining the length of the test.

Etsey (2012) suggested an eight steps approach to the construction of test items which include: (1) the test developer should first define the purpose of the test, (2) determine the item format to use, (3) determine what is to be tested, (4) write the individual items, (5) review the items, (6) prepare the scoring key, (7) write directions, and (8) evaluate the test. Inko-Tariah and Okon (2019) gave some steps in test

construction as test planning, item writing, trial testing, thereafter item analysis and items selection. The planning of the test includes the following steps: designing of the achievement test, objectives of the test, content of the test, nature of the test items, criteria for scoring the test, etc (Ahmad, Sultana & Jamil, 2020). The very next step is to develop items bank by keeping in view the specific learning objectives (knowledge, comprehension, and application). Writing of test items requires expertise on the part of test maker. Osadebe (2014) construct test with procedures such as planning, item writing, item analysis, composition of items, test theory, reliability, printing and manual preparation. These procedures used to identify the content area, format and table specification on the test.

Planning the test is a very important step in the construction of an achievement test (Obilor & Akpan, 2020). In design stage all of the important overall decisions about the test are made. These decisions include: affirming test philosophy; determining; identifying logistical and administrative constrains on test design (including test length and test timing); identifying relevant legal considerations that affect test design; establishing a validation foundation for the test; designing test specifications; and reviewing, refining, and reaffirming validity evidence for test design. Therefore, suitable with these steps in developing test above, the development of the mathematics learning test uses the following steps: (1) determination of the test objectives, (2) the preparation of the test grille (test specification), (3) writing test, (4) review and revision of questions, (5) field trials, (6) test selection, (7) test assembly, (8) test presentation, (9) scoring, and (10) reporting results test (Pandora, Sugiman & Mardapi, 2017).

Teachers' competence in Test construction

The importance of teachers setting appropriate tests for their students is inarguable considering the value of test scores given by teachers (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). Teachers should competent in teaching to give the best result consistent with best practice. That are the reasons why this study conducted to assess the teachers' knowledge in test construction and validation procedure to know how teachers are competent in developing test items. So the teachers can evaluate the lack of their teaching method, materials, knowledge and attitude toward students (Rivai, Ridwan, Supriyati & Rahmawati, 2019). Others study demonstrated proficiency in assessment skills of the participants. Results showed teachers rating themselves higher than principals while principals rated themselves higher than supervisors. Generally, it was found that they all needed more training in test construction skill.

Rohaani, Taconis and Jochems (2012) claim that teacher knowledge on the subject plays an important role in influencing students' understanding. Therefore, it is suggested that a focus on developing knowledge on the subject will affect the level of confidence in teaching positively and can improve student achievement. Furthermore, Minor (2016), shows that high-quality teachers are confident and are better to answer student questions and focus on learning because they are supported by strong knowledge. They are more likely to provide deep and meaningful engagement with the subject. In order to assess both the success of students in learning process and the teacher in the teaching, assessment instruments must be used that include instruments made by the teacher which is high quality, reliable, and can be validated (Rivai et al, 2019). The validity of a test refers to whether the test measures what it is intended to measure. (Anikweze, 2018). It depends on the purpose for which the test was developed. Okoye (2013) defined validity as a measure of the extent to which the test measures what it intends to measure. Validity refers to the ability of a test to measure what it was designed to measure (Obilor & Akpan, 2020). In term of measurement, validity is the ability of an instrument to measure what it is supposed to measure (Ahmed et al, 2020). Ukwuoma and Onah (2020), opined that validity is the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretations of test scores entailed by proposed uses of the test. a valid assessment measures what it was designed to measure and results in defensible and accurate interpretations for the intended purposes. (Dembitzer, Zelikovitz & Kettler, 2017).

In the simplest terms, a test can be judged valid if it measures what it is intended to measure (Hathcoat, 2013). The validity of an assessment tool is the extent to which the evidence produced supports the making of valid or accurate inferences. There are many forms of validity including consequential validity (the consequences for learners and teachers) and criterion validity (the criteria for judging the performance of a learner) (Newhouse, 2016). It is the degree to which the results are truthful. It implies the appropriateness, meaningful, and usefulness of any inference made from a test score (Anikweze,

2018). Qualitative research is based on the fact that validity is a matter of trustworthiness, utility, and dependability (Zohrabi, 2013). It encompasses the entire experimental concept, and establishes whether the results obtained meet all of the requirements of the scientific research method (Haradhan, 2017).

Masuwai and Sa'ad (2017) argued that most educational researchers and evaluators presented their work without sufficient evidence of validation. As educational research and evaluation studies received growing recognition in the field of teaching and learning, particularly in assessing students' learning outcomes and teachers' effectiveness, the process through which the validity and reality of the instrument was established are crucial in deciding the effectiveness of the instrument in assessment (Ibrahim & Wun, 2020). Thus, a valid test must be appropriate to the level of the testees and satisfy the comprehensiveness of course content (Anikweze, 2018). Hemant and Poonam (2017) discusses about types of validity are (i) Content validity, (ii) Face validity, (iii) Criterion related validity, and (iv) Construct validity.

Content validity: Content validity refers to the comprehensiveness of the instrument in covering the content areas that have been treated during instruction (Anikweze, 2018). According to Yusoff (2019) content validity is defined as the degree to which elements of an assessment instrument are relevant to and representative of the targeted construct for a particular assessment purpose. It can be seen as the extent to which the items on a test are fairly representative of the entire domain the test seeks to measure. Content validity or sampling validity ensures that a test covers broad areas of the syllabus (Kinyua & Okunya, 2014). When a test has content validity, the items on the test should represent all the range of possible items the test should cover (Abdullahi, 2019). A content valid test measures what it is projected to measure the content as depicted by the test blueprint. The tests in the field of education are generally constructed to measure some specific qualities or abilities (variables) of the students.

Statement of the Problem

The present senior secondary school curricula demand that variety of assessments be carried out in the course of instruction to guide effective teaching. Sequel to this and the relatively scanty number of instruments for measuring students' achievement in Mathematics at secondary school level, teachers of the subject have continued to develop instruments for measuring students' achievement in the subject. Most teachers hurriedly copy questions from any past question paper to compose their summative achievement tests. As a result, teachers do not establish validity and reliability for such tests. Students are often assessed with poorly prepared achievement tests by their Mathematics teachers. The content areas of their tests in Mathematics are not spread out to cover the content of Mathematics curriculum.

Observations show that those teacher-developed testing instruments are generally of doubtful psychometric features since no serious attention might have been paid to their test construction and validation. For such instruments, either face validation or possibly construct validation was employed. Most of the Mathematics teachers in secondary schools do not seem to possess the competencies required in instrument development and validation. This means that for Mathematics teachers to use valid and reliable tests, experts in test construction have to develop them, otherwise the objective of our education system may not be achieved. Students are examined at every level of the senior secondary school with teachers made achievement tests until the end of the third year when they are finally assessed by WACE or NECO.

Consequently, such tests limit students' scope of reading and this leads to poor achievement in Mathematics. Students' good achievement in Mathematics at SSCE will depend to a large extent, coverage of the Mathematics curriculum as well as the use of valid and reliable Mathematics Achievement Tests to assess them. Therefore, it was as a result of the use of unreliable achievement test poorly designed by Mathematics teachers, and the need to provide a more valid and reliable Mathematics achievement test in senior secondary school, that the researcher conceived the idea to carry out a research on assessment of teachers' knowledge of test construction and validation procedures in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto central senatorial district of Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study will be to:

1. Assess the teachers' knowledge of test construction procedure based on professional training in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

2. Assess the teachers' knowledge of validation procedure based on years of working experience in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study will answer the following research questions:

- i. To what extent are teachers' knowledgeable in test construction procedure based on professional training in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent are teachers' knowledgeable in validation procedure based on years of working experience in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted survey research design. Anikweze (2013) stated that surveys are applicable to the assessment of attitudes, achievements, feelings, opinions and perceptions of a large number of people at a particular time. Surveys are also used to measure any number of variables in a natural setting. It is the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions. This design was employed because the interest of the researcher is to examine and describe a certain variable in relation to a certain population. The survey has capacity to gather different set of data at the same time from the sample that were considered for the study to justify current condition and practice and make more plans for improving them. Therefore, this study adopted this design because it sought to obtain information from a representative sample of the population. The population of this study comprises of 1,787 senior secondary schools' Mathematics teachers of Sokoto State. The state has three senatorial districts (Sokoto East, Sokoto South and Sokoto Central senatorial zones) with four education zones which covered the state (Sokoto North, Sokoto Central, Sokoto East, and Sokoto West education zones) (See Appendix II). The population obtained from one hundred and forty-five (145) senior secondary schools from four education zones, and the target population of the study obtained from sixteen (16) senior secondary schools with a total number of two hundred and twenty-five (225) Mathematics teacher in Sokoto State. The choice of the population was because all mathematics teachers in the study area

Table 2: Population distribution according to local government area and schools

S/No.	School	LGA	No of Teachers
1.	GDSS Alu Quarters Bado	Wamakko	17
2.	GDSS Birjingo	Goranya	15
3.	GDSS Illela	Illela	7
4.	GDSS Kurawa	Sabon Birni	16
5.	GDSS Maberu	Sokoto South	17
6.	GDSS Rabah	Rabah	13
7.	GDSS Romon Sarki	Tambuwal	15
8.	GDSS Sifawa	Bodinga	17
9.	GDSS Silame	Silame	14
10.	GDSS Tudun Yola	Sokoto North	19
11.	GDSS Turba	Isa	11
12.	GGASS Isa	Isa	9
13.	GGDSS Bodinga	Bodinga	13
14.	GGDSS Kware	Kware	15
15.	GGSS Sanyinna	Tambuwal	14
16.	GTC Binji	Binji	13
Total			225

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Education Summary (2024)

The sampling technique used in the study was Cluster sampling technique in the selection of education zone, and simple random sampling technique was employed to select (4) schools from each education zone, making a total number of sixteen (16) schools. Simple random sampling was also used in selecting the participants where every participant has equal chance of being selected. The sample of 132 mathematics teachers were drawn using Research Advisors (2006) table for determining the sample size,

and the sample of teachers in each school was selected proportionally according to the population of teachers in the schools selected for the study. The sample size distribution was presented in Table 3.

iii. Table 3: Sample distribution of teachers by school and local government area

S/No.	School	LGA	Sample Size
1.	GDSS Alu Quarters Bado	Wamakko	10
2.	GDSS Birjingo	Goranya	9
3.	GDSS Illela	Illela	4
4.	GDSS Kurawa	Sabon Birni	9
5.	GDSS Maberu	Sokoto South	10
6.	GDSS Rabah	Rabah	8
7.	GDSS Romon Sarki	Tambuwal	9
8.	GDSS Sifawa	Bodinga	10
9.	GDSS Silame	Silame	8
10.	GDSS Tudun Yola	Sokoto North	11
11.	GDSS Turba	Isa	6
12.	GGASS Isa	Isa	5
13.	GGDSS Bodinga	Bodinga	8
14.	GGDSS Kware	Kware	9
15.	GGSS Sanyinna	Tambuwal	8
16.	GTC Binji	Binji	8
Total			132

The instrument for data collection were: Test Construction and Standardization of Mathematics Test Questionnaire (TCSMTQ) adapted from Abdullahi (2019). The questionnaire consists of sections A and B. Sections A consists the bio-data of the respondents as follows: name of school, gender, educational qualification and years of working experience, while section B consists 32 items that measured teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test. The questionnaire was adopted the Likert format. Each item of the questionnaire was responded using a four point Likert Scale with the following responses: Always (A), Almost Always (AA), Sometimes (ST), and Not at All (NA). The responses were scored as (A) = 4, (AA) = 3, (ST) = 2, and (NA) = 1. Teachers was required to objectively express their opinions using the four point Likert Scale. The instrument (questionnaire) used for data collection for the study was already validated by its original author (Abdullahi, 2019). Despite the validation by the original author (Abdullahi, 2019), the researcher still consulted experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for their consent about using the instrument (questionnaire). The corrections made by these experts were properly effected before the researcher used it as a valid instrument for the study. The reliability of the instrument (questionnaire) was already determined by its original author Abdullahi (2019). The author used Cronbach's alpha coefficient to test the internal consistency of the instrument (questionnaire). A coefficient of 0.82 indicated a high degree of internal consistency of the instrument (questionnaire). Also, the instrument (TCSMTQ) was tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha method by the researcher. The result showed that the instrument was highly reliable with a reliability coefficient of 0.75. The researcher collected a letter of introduction titled "Students' Field Research" from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to Sokoto State Ministry of Education. After approval from the Ministry of Education. The researcher visited all the sampled schools with approval letter for conducting research to collect data for the study. During the process of administration of the instrument, the researcher with the help of research assistant in each school distributed the questionnaire to the participants. The researcher explained the instructions verbally and allowed them to read the written instructions. The researcher also gave them room for asking questions for further clarification. The questionnaires were collected after filling by the participants to ensure 100% retrieve and finally, the instrument was subjected for further analysis. The data collected for this study were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Frequencies and percentages was used to describe the

demographic variable of the participants. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Independent sampled t-test was used to test hypothesis one, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was also used to test hypotheses two and three. All hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULT

This section presents the mean and standard deviation of the mathematics teachers.

Research Question One: *How do teachers' competence in test construction are based on professional training among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria?*

Table 7: Mean and standard deviation of Mathematics teachers with respect to their professional training on the competence of test construction.

Professional training	N	Mean	SD
Professional Teachers	94	54.32	5.961
Non-professional Teachers	38	50.92	7.046

Table 1 shows the mean score of 54.32 and standard deviation of 5.961 for professional teachers, while mean score of 50.92 with a standard deviation of 7.046 for non-professional teachers respectively. The table indicates that the mean for non-professional teachers is lower than that of professional teachers, while the standard deviation of non-professional teachers is higher than that of professional teachers. This result clearly showed that professional teachers were competence in test construction among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *How do teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test are based on working experience among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of Mathematics teachers with respect to their years of working experience on the competence in standardization of Mathematics test.

Working Experience	N	Mean	SD
0-9 Years	57	37.14	5.174
10-19 Years	41	37.76	4.721
20-29 Years	25	38.00	4.950
30 Years and Above	9	39.44	4.746

Table 2 shows the mean score of 37.14 and standard deviation of 5.174 for mathematics teachers with 0-9 years, mean score of 37.76 with a standard deviation of 4.721 for teachers with 10-19 years, while mean score of 38.00 with a standard deviation of 4.950 for teachers with 20-29 years and mean score of 39.44 with a standard deviation of 4.746 for teachers with 30 years and above respectively. The table indicates that the mean for teachers with 0-9 years, and 10-19 years and is lower than that of 20-29 and 30 years and above, while the standard deviation of 0-9 years and 20-29 years is higher than that of 10-19 years and 30 years and above. This result clearly showed that mathematics teachers with 20-29 and 30 and above years of working experience were competence in standardization of Mathematics test among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Table 12(b): Scheffe's test showing the difference in the mean score of test construction competence and standardization of Mathematics test based on educational qualifications.

Level of Qualifications (I)	Level of Qualifications (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Diploma	NCE	-1.5322	1.34970	.863
	HND	3.1143	1.63411	.460
	Degree	-.2279	1.38561	1.000
	Higher Degree	-3.6833	2.03809	.516
NCE	Diploma	1.5322	1.34970	.863
	HND	4.6465*	1.17330	.004
	Degree	1.3043	.79137	.607

	Higher Degree	-2.1511	1.69120	.805
	Diploma	-3.1143	1.63411	.460
HND	NCE	-4.6465*	1.17330	.004
	Degree	-3.3422	1.21445	.112
	Higher Degree	-6.7976*	1.92581	.016
	Diploma	.2279	1.38561	1.000
Degree	NCE	-1.3043	.79137	.607
	HND	3.3422	1.21445	.112
	Higher Degree	-3.4554	1.71999	.403
	Diploma	3.6833	2.03809	.516
Higher Degree	NCE	2.1511	1.69120	.805
	HND	6.7976*	1.92581	.016
	Degree	3.4554	1.71999	.403

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The Scheffe's test in Table 12(b) further revealed that significant difference exists in the mean score of test construction competence and standardization of Mathematics test between NCE and HND, Higher Degree and HND holders ($p = 0.004$ and $0.016 < 0.05$). Therefore, the teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test differ significantly between HND and those with NCE and Higher Degree holders in their level of qualifications.

Summary of Findings

The following are the summary of findings from the study:

1. There is a significant difference in teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria ($p = 0.006 < 0.05$).
2. There is no significant difference in teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test based on working experience among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria ($p = 0.591 > 0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study:

1. There exists a significant difference between professional and non-professional teacher. Professional teachers were better than non-professional teachers in construction of the test items. This shows that, teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training among senior secondary schools' teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria differ significantly.
2. There is no significant difference between Mathematics teachers with different years of working experience in standardization of Mathematics test items. This shows that, teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test based on years of working experience among senior secondary schools' teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria did not differ significantly.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. For the professional growth of Mathematics teachers, the State' Ministry of Education should organize conferences, seminars, workshops, and given pre and in-service professional training programmes on test construction to non-professional teachers.
2. Mathematics teachers with different years of working experience should ensure that the test items sample the topics and sub-topics covered in the contents and ensure that the items are valid and reliable.

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